

**NEURODEVELOPMENTAL SCREENING
OF FIVE-YEAR-OLD CHILDREN**

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The neurodevelopmental examination takes about 15-20 minutes if the child co-operates. The tasks given test vision, squint, gross and fine motor performance, co-ordination and balance, involuntary movements, upper motor neuron disturbances, articulation and language skills, perception, concentration, and behaviour. Points are given for incomplete and unsuccessful performances. The total number of points shows the degree of disturbance of the child's neuropsychological development.

The examination itself is easy to perform. However, it demands a thorough knowledge of how to score the performance of the tasks, and what a five-year-old child is able to do within the limits of normal development.

Visual acuity. Vision is examined by means of an E-table or, preferably, the Sheridan-Gardiner 7-letter table at a distance of 5-6 metres.

Squint. Eight points are given if the squint is directly apparent to the eye. A slight squint is scored 2 points and is found by the Hirschberg penlamp test. The investigator holds a pocket flashlight at a distance of about 30 cm from the subject's eye, and notes the position of the reflecting light from the patient's cornea.

Gait. Regularity of gait is controlled by walking the child along a straight line or watching him when he arrives for the examination.

Hopping on one foot. An approved performance requires 5-7 hops on the spot or within a drawn circle. Girls usually hop better than boys. However, both sexes may have difficulties in hopping on the spot.

Patting hands. The child pats the back of one hand with the other one as quickly as possible and both speed and regularity are observed. An approved performance requires at least 12 pats in 5 seconds.

Pencil grip. Five-year-old children usually have a three-finger tripod grip. A fist grip or a grip high on the pencil (marked as clumsy) is scored incorrect.

Heel-toe walking. Not all five-year-old children can do this perfectly along a straight line, and therefore are one or two side-steps allowed.

Finger-nose pointing. The investigator observes whether the child has intention tremor, choreoathetosis or other involuntary movements. The best performance is counted, not the first possible clumsy attempts.

Diadochokinesis. The test is performed first separately on each side and then concomitantly on both sides. The child is asked to keep his upper extremity bent 90 degrees from the elbow along his side with fingers straight ahead. He is also told not to move his elbow and not to press it against the body. The regularity of the pronation/supination movements, and all possible associated movements in either upper extremity are observed. As a rule, associated movements can still be seen in five-year-old children. In the control group 17 children were awarded 0-3 points, 33 were given 4-7 points, and two children 8 points.

Standing with arms extended. The child stands with his feet together, arms stretched out straight forwards, palms downwards, fingers spread and extended, and eyes closed. The child is also asked not to move his fingers. Balance and possible asymmetry, upward and downward movement of the arms, and involuntary movements (choreiform movements, athetosis) are observed.

Tongue tremor. The child is asked to keep his tongue out and as still as possible for about 20 seconds. Possible tongue tremor is observed. Slight motion of the tongue is not considered abnormal.

Tongue impersistence is the child's ability to keep the tongue protruded for 20 seconds.

Facial asymmetry. In order to detect possible asymmetry in the facial muscles the child is asked to grimace, close his eyes, etc.

Reflexes. Three reflexes (biceps, brachio-radialis, and knee-jerk) are examined on both sides and both vivacity and possible asymmetry are observed. Multiple reflexes, the lack of reflexes when the child is fully relaxed, and asymmetry are marked as abnormal.

Articulation. The substitution of consonants (s,r,l,k,d,ks) is examined both in single words and in sentences. The child is asked to repeat single words and if any sound is pronounced incorrectly the child is asked to pronounce the single consonants. If a single incorrect consonant is noticed, no points are given for incorrect pronunciation of this consonant in words. However, the pronunciation of words is scored incorrect if other errors are noticed, as reversals and substitution may occur in sentences although they are normal in single words.

Forming sentences on his own initiative. This skill can be ascertained while testing the child but can also be observed when

he is asked to tell about his daily doings or by showing pictures which can be discussed.

Repeating sentences. The child can be asked to repeat some simple sentence, for instance "two cats run on the street". This ensures that the child understands the instruction. The test sentence is "The shining kite flies above the trees. Fem ekorrar skuttade bland trädens grenar".

Speech comprehension. This is observed during the whole examination.

Drawing. The child is shown drawings of a circle, square and triangle. Generally, the child can copy the circle and the square, but may have difficulties in drawing the triangle.

Imitation of gestures. Different pictures of the upper extremities are shown to the child according to items 5-6 and 7-8 by Berges and Lezine. No points are given if the child imitates the postures in a form which is not a mirror image.

Reed hearing test. Words are whispered behind the child at a distance of two metres from both the right and the left side. The child keeps his hand against the ear not being tested and points at a picture corresponding to the word whispered by the investigator. The pictures are on a table in front of the child. The words are selected to include both high and low frequencies. The words are fish, dish, ship, pig, - klocka, socka, kyrka, flicka. If the child

fails in the Reed hearing test it has to be decided if it is because of poor hearing or a deficiency in auditory perception.

Behaviour. Aggressiveness towards the physician can reflect a serious disturbance of behaviour. However, shyness and guardedness do not necessarily mean a behavioural disturbance and may reflect the physician's own ability to co-operate with a five-year-old child. It is also important in evaluating behaviour and concentration ability to note if the child is tired or hungry at the time of the examination.

Total score. When the total score of the screening examination has been summed, attention must be paid to tasks for which the points were given. For instance if the points were awarded mostly for vision and squint the child needs to be examined by an ophthalmologist, but if high scores are from many different subgroups it is evident that the child needs further investigation by a paediatrician or a paediatric neurologist.

The requisites. Equipment for examining vision, and a penlamp for squint. Pen, pencil, and paper. Cards with drawings of a circle, square and triangle. Pictures needed for the Reed hearing test. Reflex hammer.

Order of examination. The test can most conveniently be made in the following order:

- the child sitting: copying forms, repetition of words and sentences, tongue tremor, facial asymmetry, squint, imitation of gestures, finger-nose pointing, Reed hearing test.
- the child standing: gait, hopping on one foot, standing with arms extended, patting hands, diadochokinesis, vision.
- the child lying: reflexes. They can also be examined when the child is sitting if the child is able to relax.

Vocabulary.

- Ataxia: broad-striped gait, uncertainty when turning (lack of co-ordination of voluntary muscular movements).
- Athetotic movements: relatively slow, writhing, repetitive involuntary gross movements.
- Intention tremor: tremor on attempting voluntary movements, ataxia of upper extremities.
- Choreiform movements: rapid, irregular, involuntary movements.

Recommendable additional tests. Walking on heels. Hopping alternating feet together, feet apart. Count fingers. Build models with cubes. Draw-a-person.

EXAMINATION FORM

NAME _____ AGE _____

VISION	right	?	0	1	3	5	7	8	8	8
	left	?	0	1	3	5	7	8	8	8
		?	6/6	6/9	6/12	6/18	6/24	6/36	6/60	blind

SQUINT	?	0	2	8
	?	no	slight	clear or operated

GROSS MOTOR PERFORMANCE	WALKING	even pace	?	0	4	16
			?	yes	diffic.	cannot
HOPPING	right foot	?	0	2	3	4
	left foot	?	0	2	3	4
		?	stable	instable	diffic.	cannot

FINE MOTOR PERFORMANCE	PATTING	right pats left	?	0	2	3
		left pats right	?	0	2	3
		?	regular	irregul.	cannot	
	PENCIL GRIP	sped, right	?	0	2	
		speed, left	?	0	2	
		?	≥12/5s	<12/5s		
		?	0	4	8	
		?	normal	clumsy	fisted	

CO-ORDINATION AND BALANCE	HEEL-TOE WALKING	?	0	4	8
		?	stable	instable	cannot
FINGER-NOSE POINTING	right	?	0	4	8
	left	?	0	4	8
		?	stable	instable	cannot
DIADOCHOKINESIS	right	?	0	1	3
	left	?	0	1	3
	both	?	0	2	4
		?	regular	irregular	cannot
ASSOCIATIVE MOVEMENTS	right	?	0	1	2
	left	?	0	1	2
	both	?	0	1	2
		?	no	right/left	both
TONGUE TREMOR	?	0	8		
	?	no	yes		

INVOLUNTARY MOVEMENTS	STANDING WITH ARMS EXTENDED	?	0	3	8
		?	normal	choreif.	athetosis

UPPER MOTOR NEURON DISTURBANCES	STANDING WITH ARMS EXTENDED	?	0	6			
		?	0	4			
		?	normal	asymmetry			
REFLEXES	BICEPS	right	?	0	2	2	2
		left	?	0	2	2	2
	BRACHIORADIALIS	right	?	0	2	2	2
		left	?	0	2	2	2
	KNEE JERK	right	?	0	2	2	2
		left	?	0	2	2	2
		?	+	+++	-	asymm.	

ARTICULATION	CONSONANTS	d	?	0	1
		k	?	0	1
		ks	?	0	1
		l	?	0	1
		r	?	0	1
		s	?	0	1
	SINGLE WORDS	?	?	0	4
	SENTENCES	?	?	0	4
		?	normal	abnormal	

LANGUAGE SKILLS	FORMS SENTENCES	?	0	4	16
		?	0	2	8
	COMPREHENDS SPEECH	?	yes	not age level	no
	REPEATS SENTENCE	?	0	4	
		?	yes	no	

PERCEPTION	DRAWING	circle	?	0	4
		square	?	0	2
		triangle	?	0	2
	BERGES-LEZINE	5	?	0	4
		6	?	0	4
		7	?	0	4
		8	?	0	4
	REED HEARING TEST	?	0	8	
		?	can	cannot	

CONCENTRATION	ATTENTION SPAN	?	0	2	4
		?	0	2	4
	TONGUE IMPERSISTENCE	?	normal	somewh. short	short

BEHAVIOUR	OVERACTIVITY	?	0	2	4
		?	0	2	4
	SLOWNESS	?	0	2	4
	SHYNESS	?	0	2	4
		?	no	somewhat	yes
	AGGRESSIVENESS	?	0	8	
	GUARDEDNESS	?	0	2	
	UNWILLINGNESS	?	0	4	
		?	no	yes	

TOTAL SCORE _____

CONCLUSIONS _____